

Formation of Single Boundary and Double Boundary on Electrolysis of Cr(VI) Solutions

SANTI R. PALIT and MAYA GUHA

Department of Physical Chemistry, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Jadavpur, Calcutta-32

Manuscript received 7 November 1973; accepted 13 February 1974

As with many dye solutions¹, electrolysis of chromate and dichromate solutions in simple U-tubes and double bent U-tubes (W-tubes) results in formation of sharp boundaries. In a simple U-tube a single sharp boundary is formed right near the cathode bend separating the deep brown acidic solution from the pale yellow alkaline solution whereas in a W-tube two sharp boundaries are formed dividing the solution into three zones, pale yellow alkaline zone, colourless and neutral central zone and deep brown acidic zone. The formation of such a colourless central zone is evidently an anti-Hittorf phenomenon. These sharp boundaries remain stationary with passage of current. Results obtained from a study of the effects of electrolyte concentration, current strength and cell geometry on the development of single boundary and double boundary phenomena with Cr(VI) solutions have been described.

IT has lately been reported by Palit¹ that many dyes (and some coloured inorganic salts) form on electrolysis in a U-tube a sharp boundary in the cathode limb between a deeply coloured acid solution and a lightly coloured alkaline solution. Instead of a single boundary two very sharp boundaries (the colour sequence from anode to cathode being a deeply coloured acid solution/a colourless neutral solution/a lightly coloured alkaline solution) are formed if the electrolysis is conducted in a double bent U-tube (W-tube for short; Fig. 2). Chromate or dichromate is very convenient for such studies not only because it shows this beautiful phenomenon very easily but also because unlike dyes and many other inorganic salts it is resistant to electrolytic reduction or oxidation under ordinary conditions. We report here some detailed results with this system to supplement our aforementioned work^{1,2}. Most of the experiments are simple enough for lecture demonstration, and so it is strange how such a simple and beautiful property of electrolytes has so far gone unnoticed.

Formation of Single Boundary (U-tube Experiments) :

The process of boundary formation in a U-tube can be generally described as follows. On sending a small direct current through a solution of a chromate or a dichromate contained in a U-tube (Fig. 1), the solution in the cathode compartment extending over the region CB becomes progressively lighter and yellowish in colour, and the solution on the anode side extending over the region AB progressively becomes deeper and brownish in colour. The current in most cases tends to increase somewhat with time, eventually, the time depending on the concentration, current strength, size of the U-tube etc., a sharp boundary between a lower brown solution (the colour of chromic acid) and an upper greenish yellow solution

(the colour of dilute alkaline chromate solution) is observed to form at or near B.

The formation of the boundary is somewhat unexpected due to the following reasons. The Cr(VI) anions are expected to migrate to the anode and so an anode zone of chromic acid is expected and not

Fig. 1, U—Tube

such a long column AB of chromic acid of, as far as can be visually judged, uniform concentration throughout. Secondly, all Cr(VI) ions are expected to migrate to the anode. This is evidently not so as is seen from the fact that a considerable proportion of the Cr(VI) ions (usually about one-third or less) is left out in the cathode solution CB after boundary

formation and they continue to remain there uniformly distributed showing only a small tendency to migrate, though the current may be continued for days after boundary formation to the extent of sending at least one hundred times the current equivalent of the Cr(VI) ions present in CB. Apparently, the residual Cr(VI) ions in CB have largely lost their ionic mobility, though intrinsically it is not so. This is seen from the fact that if a portion of CB is pipetted out and a current is sent through, these ions migrate as expected. Evidently, after boundary formation there is some process not involving the migration of Cr(VI) ions which carries the electric current.

Some data showing the effect of various factors are shown in Table I. The salient features can be summarised as follows.

(i) The higher the concentration, the longer is the time necessary for boundary formation, provided the current is sufficiently strong.

(ii) The higher the current, the quicker is the boundary formation and the sharper is the boundary. Too low current fails to produce boundary within a reasonable time and too high a current say, above 50 ma is unsuitable as it tends to heat up the solution perceptibly producing convectional disturbance.

(iii) Under otherwise same condition the boundary appears quicker in a narrow tube than in a wide tube evidently due to higher current flux per unit area. This effect is so much that a lecture demonstration of single boundary formation (i.e. formation within a lecture period of 1 hr) can be easily given with a narrow tube say, of 10 mm diam. with 10 ma current.

(iv) As already pointed out the residual concentration of Cr(VI) ion in CB is about half to one-third of the original and as expected is higher with higher initial concentration.

Two very usual and interesting property of the boundary, to be called counter-diffusion and persistence should be noted. Firstly, if the current is stopped the two solutions interdiffuse, and in less than a day (sometimes only in a few hrs) the boundary vanishes and the whole U-tube reverts back to a uniform colour. This counter diffusion is very surprising because if a boundary between two such solutions is artificially made by carefully pouring one solution over another it remains fairly sharp for days and requires weeks for thorough inter-diffusion. The property of persistence is that if a few ml of say, the anode solution, is slowly pipetted out, the boundary instead of getting displaced towards the anode remains almost in the same place. It appears that once formed there is an inherent tendency of the boundary to persist in the same place, and it tends to retain its "equilibrium position" even when some solution is removed from either of the two limbs.

The reality of "equilibrium position" of the boundary is also shown by the following facts. If the cathode limb is filled with the dichromate solution and the anode limb with water, on electrolysis the same final position of the boundary is arrived at. On the other hand, if the starting situation is reverse, i.e., the cathode limb contains water and the anode limb the dichromate solution, a boundary at the usual place is still obtained but the CB column would be colourless instead of pale greenish yellow. Even if the anode solution contains the dichromate extending over only say, an inch or two at the top of AB, on establishing the current the anions would make the unusual movement towards the cathode with progress of electrolysis until it spreads out uniformly over AB. Evidently, there is a strong tendency to form a boundary somewhere near B irrespective of the original distribution of the dichromate,

TABLE I(A) (U—Tube)

Electrolyte Concentration	Current ma	Approximate time for boundary formation	Position of Boundary	Comments about Boundary (B)
N/10 K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	10	3 hrs	B	sharp
N/20 K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	10	1 hr	B	sharp
N/40 K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	10	1 hr	B	sharp
N/10 K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	5	1 day	B	not sharp
N/20 K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	5	3 hrs	B	sharp
N/40 K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	5	2 hrs	B	sharp
N/10 K ₂ CrO ₄	10	Overnight	D	Boundary starts from A and settles finally to D.
N/20 K ₂ CrO ₄	10	Overnight	D	
N/40 K ₂ CrO ₄	10	2 hrs	D	
N/10, N/20, N/40 K ₂ CrO ₄	2	More than 2 days for each	D	
N/10, N/20, N/40 Chromic Acid	10	4 days, 2 days, 2 days	Between C and B	Boundary starts from C; colourless/Brown.
"	2	2 days for each	"	

TABLE I(B)

Electrolyte Concentration	Diameter of the tube	Current ma	Time for boundary formation	Comments about boundary
N/20 K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	22 mm	5	3 hrs	sharp
N/20 K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	10 mm	5	55 mins	sharp
N/20 K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	6 mm	5	25 mins.	sharp

even if it needs the anions apparently to move towards the cathode.

If chromate is used in place of dichromate the result is somewhat different. The boundary starts from the top of the anode column and finally settles somewhere near the bottom of the anode limb, say, at D. This is the result of the general tendency of the boundary to get shifted towards anode on adding alkali, and towards cathode on adding acid. However, if the starting solution is chromic acid instead of dichromate, some marked differences are observed. The boundary (here, pale coloured to colourless/deep coloured) would form at the top of the cathode column CB and would move towards the anode until its equilibrium boundary position somewhere near B in CB is reached. This however takes a very long time, usually a few days and the current becomes very small by then.

from anode to cathode would be deep brown/colourless at B₂ and colourless/pale greenish yellow at B₁. The pH sequence is acidic (AB₂) of pH about 2.5 to 3.5 followed by the neutral colourless zone B₂B₁ of pH about 6.5 to 7.2 which in its turn is followed

Fig. 2. W-Tube

Formation of Double Boundary (W-tube Experiments) :

If the above experiments are conducted in a double bent U-tube (Fig. 2), to be called W-tube for brevity, the results are somewhat different but more spectacular. A sharp boundary first forms somewhere near B₁ more or less in the same manner as in a U-tube, the solution B₁C being pale mustard yellow (alkaline chromate colour) and the solution AB₁ being deep brown (chromic acid colour). On continuing the current a faint boundary appears at or near B₂ and the portion B₁B₂ starts getting depleted of its colour and eventually (usually overnight) becomes colourless, so that two boundaries are observed, one at B₁ and another at B₂. B₁ often tends to be at a lower level than B₂. The colour sequence

by the alkaline zone CB₁ of pH about 11. It should be pointed out that Hittorf mechanism allows fall of

TABLE 2(A) W-TUBE

Electrolyte Concentration	Current ma	Time for single boundary formation (approx.)	Time for double boundary formation (approx.)	Position of Boundary	Comments about Boundary (B)
N/10, N/20, N/40 K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	10	3 hrs, 2 hrs, 2 hrs.	26 hrs, 17 hrs and 6 hrs. respectively.	B ₁ and B ₂	sharp
N/10, N/20, N/40 K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	5	3 hrs, 2½ hrs, 1 hr.	-, 25 hrs. overnight	B ₁ and B ₂	sharp
N/10, N/20, N/40 K ₂ CrO ₄	10	B. starts in 5 mins from A in all cases.	Overnight	B ₁ and B ₂	Boundary starts from A and settles at B ₂ , B ₁ appears later.
N/10, N/20, N/40 Chromic acid	10	2 days, 1 day, 1 day		Between C and B ₁ but usually near C.	Boundary starts from C, no double boundary.

TABLE 2(B)

Electrolyte Concentration	Diameter of the tube	Current ma	Time for single boundary formation	Time for double boundary formation	Comments about boundary
N/20 K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	22 mm	4	5 hrs.	Overnight	Double boundary at B ₁ and B ₂ .
N/20 K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	14 mm	4	4 hrs.	Overnight	Double boundary at B ₁ and B ₂
N/20 K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	8 mm	4	½ hr.	5 hrs	Double boundary at B ₁ and B ₂ .

concentration round the electrodes only and not in the intermediate zone, whereas here a more or less complete depletion takes place in the intermediate zone. So in this sense it is an anti-Hittorf behaviour which appears not to have been anticipated or reported before.

If the current is still prolonged at a small value of about 1 ma nothing would appear to happen further as if the residual Cr(VI) ions in CB have almost lost their ionic mobility before an impervious column B_1B_2 of water. This is an interesting situation which is difficult to understand with reference to the conventional ion transport mechanism of current conduction. Evidently, after formation of double boundary the current as long as it is small is carried by ions other than Cr(VI) ions, most probably by hydrogen and hydroxyl ions. At higher current strength of about 10 ma or higher, the Cr(VI) ions migrate though rather slowly until the whole region B_2C becomes colourless which takes about a week or so.

The effect of change of concentration, current strength and tube diameter in a W-tube is similar to that in a U-tube. We report some typical values in Table 2. There is however one noticeable difference between a U-tube and a W-tube. The boundaries in a W-tube are generally extremely sharp, much sharper than in the case of a U-tube.

It is further to be noted that whatever be the initial distribution of the dichromate (or chromate),

the final condition after the current is sent for a sufficient length of time is the same. So, if the W-tube is filled up on the cathode side with the dichromate and the rest with water to start with, we end up with a chromic acid solution free of metal ions on the anode side, sharply separated from the dilute alkaline chromate solution in CB_1 by a column of water, B_2B_1 . This provides a simple method of preparing dye acids and inorganic complex acids, such as ferricyanic acid, ferrocyanic acid, etc. free from metallic cations. It may be mentioned that ordinary colourless salts such as say, sodium sulphate also form these three zones of sharply differing pH on electrolysis in a W-tube for a sufficiently long time, though it is not possible to have an easy visual indication of the same. It would be of interest to try to detect such boundaries by using Schlieren technique or radioactive tracers.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Shri Prithwis Kumar Basu and Mrs. Manika Dutta Gupta for essential experimental assistance.

References

1. S. R. PALIT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 963.
2. S. R. PALIT, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1972, **46**, 430.